

#9

Evaluation & Impact Assessment

**WHAT, WHO, WHY,
WHERE, WHEN & HOW?**

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING INTERROGATING CREATING ADDRESSING APPLYING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>At the beginning of a project/initiative, at the planning stage.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Whole multi-actor group, small to large. Particularly useful for large consortia who are challenged with coordinating a consistent multi-actor approach across many tasks.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>Some technical skills required, involving the use of a simple template (MS Excel), maintained online.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>Approx 1-2 hours initially (depending on the extent of the project/initiative - how many tasks etc.) with periodic maintenance throughout the lifetime of the project/initiative.</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Requires basic materials, little or no cost.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools # 1, 2, 3, 6.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: Teagasc

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Plan multi-actor tasks in advance, identifying:
 - » Which actors & stakeholders will be involved – *Who?*
 - » The tasks they will be involved in – *What?*
 - » Why would they want to be involved in such tasks – *Why?*
 - » The logistics and approach of the tasks – *Where? When? and How?*
- Challenge multi-actor consortia with implementing multi-actor tasks in a rigorous and meaningful way.
- To plan the range of multi-actor tasks and approaches used at the level of the whole project/initiative, sharing expertise and ensuring consistency.
- Plan at the level of the whole-project/initiative how the project plans to engage with its actor/stakeholder community to avoid fatigue, duplication and to maximise opportunities for synergies between tasks
- Record data iteratively on who actually was engaged with and how etc. (as per above), in a template that is periodically updated by project/initiative partners.
- To provide data for project coordinators to identify strengths in the multi-actor approach that may be shared across the project/initiative, and to identify areas for improvement.

Background and Logic

The 'multi-actor approach' (MAA) is central to the success of interactive innovation. The MAA is essentially about people from different professional and scientific backgrounds working together collaboratively and creatively combining their knowledge for innovation. LIAISON identifies ways to enhance the MAA, in the PLA manual and practice abstracts on co-learning produced by WP2, how-to guides produced by WP7 and in this current Evaluation & Impact Assessment handbook. However, particularly for large consortia implementing many tasks employing the MAA, how can all of the MAA activities be coordinated and maintained to a consistent standard?

This tool plans approaches to the MAA (who, what, why, where, when and how) at the level of a whole project/initiative. It supports a coordinated approach that ensures consistency, prevents duplication & maximises synergies; and it records data on what actually happened in MAA tasks ex-post, providing an evidence-base for evaluation in sharing strengths and addressing weaknesses.

Materials

- Sticky notes
- Thick dark markers
- MS Office Excel

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1: Preparation

- Explain the purpose, logic and background.
- Where relevant, issue to each participant a copy of the project’s/initiative’s funding contract or planning document, which identifies all tasks.
- Shown on a screen (or issue a hard copy if a screen is not available) a sample copy of the [‘Multi-Actor Recording Template’](#).

Step 2: What?

- The facilitator writes a ‘topic banner’ i.e. a title on flipchart paper – ‘What MAA Tasks?’
- Starting from the very beginning of the project and working through to the very, participants are facilitated to identify all tasks in the project/initiative that employ the MAA.
- The name of the tasks are written on post-its (by participants, with assistance where necessary) and affixed to the flipchart paper, in the sequence planned to be conducted. Where tasks are planned to occur simultaneously and of the same duration, they are placed side by side. The dates & period of implementation are written on the left hand side of the post-its (e.g. Nov 2022-Feb -2023). More flipchart paper is added to the bottom if needed, to accommodate a longer list of tasks.
- The output of Step 2 is a comprehensive list of the all MAA tasks to be undertaken, together with the dates and time-periods of implementation. Data have been gathered to populate the What tab of the MAA recording template.

Step 3: Who?

- The facilitator writes a ‘topic banner’ i.e. a title on flipchart paper – ‘Who should be involved in this MAA Task?’ (taking each task in turn, with its own flipchart paper)
- The project’s/initiative’s grant agreement/contract/plan may or may not detail the actors/stakeholders who should be involved. Consulting the agreement/contract/plan where relevant, but also brainstorming other potential actors/stakeholders, participants are facilitated to identify:
 - » The actors (who should be involved as partners) in the task, written on post its and affixed to the flipchart paper. Note that the actors are likely to include participants in the exercise who are partners in the project.
 - » The stakeholders (who should be consulted) in relation to the task, written on post its and affixed to the flipchart paper.
- The above is undertaken for each task.
- The output of Step 3 is a comprehensive list of all the actors and stakeholders who should be involved in each of the MAA tasks of the project/initiative. Data have been gathered to populate the MAA Recording Template.

AgriDemo F2F Protocol for the Multi Actor Approach

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4. AgriDemo-F2F MA Interactive Diagram & Recording Template

Example from AgriDemo: F2F (Horizon 2020 project), graphically designed. [Interactive PDF here](#)

Step 4: Why?

- At this point in the exercise, actors are invited to envision why actors/stakeholders may be motivated/incentivised to take part in the tasks. Why, from their perspectives, are they likely to want to be involved?
 - An existing, relevant 'motivations register' may be consulted/adapted for this step, following Tool #6. Tool #6 details how to build a dedicated motivations register or adapt an existing one (examples, Tool #6).
 - For each task, each actor & stakeholder type is taken in turn, and a motivations register is either:
 - » built using flipchart paper & post-its, taking each actor/stakeholder category in turn for each task, or
 - » modified (pre-existing register is viewed on screen or on paper), purusing existing content, deleting irrelevant motivations and adding new ones. Note that the facilitator may pre-prepare an existing motivations register by removing obviously irrelevant content to the project/initiative (to save time and to make the register more relevant to participants).
 - The output of Step 4 is a list of motivations, customised to each actor/stakeholder type and each tasks, detailing why they might be motivated/incentivised to participate – what is their stake? As detailed in Tool #6, this is critical information for task leaders to design and organise tasks appropriately. Data have been gathered to populate the Why tab of the MAA Recording Template.
- » Is it workwhile for the relevant task leaders to collaborate in marketing/communicating/organising/co-hosting the activities?
 - » If so, the relevant task leaders agree to come up with a plan.
- The timeline above is completed, identifying all MAA tasks taking place in the same phase of the project. Initiative, examining across them actors/stakeholders involved, potential for collaboration & added-value, and preventing actors'/stakeholders' participation fatigue (where they are engaged with repeatedly by a project/initiative).
 - The output of Step 4 is a timeline, identifying all MAA tasks and plans for collaboration (where fortuitous) assigned to task leaders. Information on where and when has been gathered for populating the MAA Recording Template.

Step 5: Where and When?

- At this step in the process, the logistical questions of *where?* and *when?* are answered, specifically in relation to the actor/stakeholder events/activities of the project.
 - They are addressed together, particularly for international projects/initiatives, as there may be possibilities to hold more than one activity/event together (for stakeholder engagement, for example).
 - The dates/rough time periods of the events/activities are identified, with reference to a grant agreement/contract/plan of a project/initiative (where relevant)
 - Then, examining all dates and time periods together, the facilitator draws a time-line, with the start date of the project at the beginning.
 - The first MAA activity is plotted on the timeline, and if other MAA activities are taking place in the same period, a discussion is facilitated on the following topics:
 - » Are we seeking to engage any of the same actor/stakeholder types in these activities?
 - » Are their motivations likely to be similar or related to enage in the (different) activities?
- This step involves considering the approaches/tools/methods that are most appropriate and effective for each MAA task/activity.
 - Show the [Multi-Actor Approach animation](#) (or circulate the video to participants)
 - The facilitator shows participants 'Multi Actor Work: Six Scenarios' (in interactive, online version of the toolbox (linked to lists of tools on Google sheets a screen, or printed lists of the tools suitable for each scenario.
 - As a guide to selecting what technique/tool/method they may consider using for a MAA task/activity, participants are invited to consider the 'Six Multi-Actor Scenarios' (pictured). What scenario/s does the planned task/activity relate to?
 - Participants select the scenario/s associated with each task. On flipchart paper with the topic banner 'How', number/s 1-6 are added. This is information for populating the How tab in the Multi-Actor Recording Template.
 - Participants can be invited to peruse (in the aftermath of the meeting) these 'easy to use' tools to facilitate multi-actor work, relevant to their task.
 - Participants may be aware of other suitable tools for use in the scenarios, and if so, they are invited to add them, preferably with a link to a reference detailing how to use the tool.
 - The output of Step 4 are details of the 'multi-actor' scenario/s to owlich their MAA relates, so that participants are guided to identify appropriate and effective tools to guide the MAA. Data are collected to populate the How tab in the Multi-Actor Recording Template.

Step 6: How?

Multi-Actor Toolbox: Online, interactive version (with links to practical tools) available [here](#).

Step 7: Using Tool#9 for Evaluation & Impact Assessment

- Following steps 1-6 above, the first iteration of a populated Multi-Actor Recording template has been completed.
- A record has been taken of each MAA task, the actors/stakeholders involved, what is likely to motivate them to be involved, where & when the activity/ies of the task will take place, and how the MAA process will be facilitated/operated. Furthermore, opportunities for tasks to collaborate in the MAA have been identified.
 - » The plans in the template for each task should be regularly revisited by task leaders in the design of project activities to compare & contrast their activities with what was originally planned (as set out in the template) and reflect on,
 - Are we engaging with the appropriate diversity of actors/stakeholders?
 - Are we responding to their motivations?
 - Are we being as efficient as possible in our engagement?
 - Are we using appropriate and effective tools to facilitate/conduct the MAA?
- » Furthermore the Multi-Actor Recording Template contains fields where task leaders enter information about what *actually* happened with regard to who was involved, how the MAA was facilitated/conducted and *when* it happened. This provides an evidence base for coordinators to continuously assess how the MAA is being conducted with a view to sharing strengths and addressing weaknesses. The record will also be of interest to project/initiative evaluators who seek evidence of a rigorous approach to the MAA.

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